

Virtual Head and Analogue Simulation: John Smeaton, 1759

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Since the 17th century, calculating and imaging are strongly intertwined in practices of analogue simulations: massive amounts of data are processed simultaneously, emerging as structures, pictures, models, or graphs which at least suggest the idea of immediate mathematics. On the level of the instruments and things, this corresponds the concept of self-recording devices. The paper reconstructs one of the initial scenes of this epistemic constellation: the analogue simulation practices of John Smeaton's water wheel models.

1,381 Experiments¹

From the spring of 1830 until December of the same year, the Franklin Institute of the State of Pennsylvania conducted 1,381 experiments on the efficiency of waterwheels. Seeing as »the circumstances, attending the action [of waterwheels], are so complicated a nature as to baffle [...the theorist's] powers of investigation,« experimentation was deemed the only path to reliable results.² The expenditure for undertaking this survey was enormous. A committee with fourteen members of the Institute was appointed to implement the project. The experimental setting allowed the researchers to test wheels in overshot, breastshot, and undershot positions, as well as to use different wheel diameters. At the end of the project, the committee's reports to the Institute's journal comprised thousands of numerical values distributed over impressive conglomeration tables of up to eighteen columns.

Nevertheless, on December 23, 1843, the Irish civil engineer Robert Mallet wrote a letter to the »London Mining Journal« in which he stated that »the Franklin Institute has added nothing important to our knowledge, beyond what the experiments of our great Smeaton, on *his* ›insignificant models‹ gave long ago.«³ This letter is only one statement in an ongoing debate on the scientific value of waterwheel experiments.⁴ And John Smeaton, the eminent

¹ This study was supported by the DFG-Kollegforschergruppe »Medienkulturen der Computersimulation« (KFOR 1927) of the Leuphana University Lüneburg.

² Anonymous, 1831, p. 146.

³ Mallet, 1844, p. 169.

⁴ Cf. Whitelaw, 1844 and Morris, 1844.

British engineer and instrument maker, had conducted his experiments almost 100 years previously. Indeed, there was a strong contradiction between Smeaton's and the Franklin Institute's approaches. While Smeaton »used a dynamic prototype of efficiency« to examine how motion should be measured, the Franklin Institute »simply measured the effect when it was done.«⁵ Although this distinction between dynamic and static measurement is far-reaching, it reveals a fundamental common ground. They both used the same method of minimizing turbulence in order to eliminate potential interference from their measurements. The better a wheel is managed, the more smoothly the water moves it. A skilled eye can thus monitor the efficiency of a waterwheel simply by watching the patterns of the water's movement. But what do we actually see when we observe flow patterns? This is the central question I will pursue in this paper. By approaching it through the mid-18th century's knowledge of waterwheels, I aim to provide support for my main argument that these measuring practices function as analogue simulation media.

Figure 1: J. Smeaton 1759: Waterwheel.

John Smeaton was a typical middle-class inventor. Born in 1724 and initially trained as an attorney, by 1748 he had opened his first shop for scientific instruments in London. During this time he improved the vacuum pump and developed a mariner's compass.⁶ When James Watt came to London five years later, Smeaton had already built his first water mill and turned to engineering as a profession. His famous publication on the »Natural Powers of

⁵ Alexander, 2008, p. 15.

⁶ Cf. Turner and Skempton, 1981, pp. 10–11.

Water and Wind to Turn Mills« was awarded the prestigious Copley Medal. The experiments on which this paper was based constituted nearly seven years of research on different types of watermills.⁷ The most prominent paper of the famous trio comprised of Antoine De Parcieux, Johann Euler, and John Smeaton, it was published in 1759 and hence some years after the other two.

Smeaton's approach to the problem of waterwheel efficiency was fully experimental. He constructed a waterwheel model with a diameter of about 0,5 m.⁸ A model river fed by a cistern 10 cm above the base and regulated by a sluice gate turned the wheel. The water was then recirculated to the reservoir by a hand pump to ensure a closed circuit. This construction – of a closed circuit of energy transformation – allowed Smeaton to start his measurements when disturbances were minimal and the wheel was running smoothly. As soon as this was the case, Smeaton would engage the rope by which the waterwheel's axle was connected via pulleys to a balance pan. By placing different weights into the pan, the load on the waterwheel and hence its velocity could be varied: once engaged, the model automatically produced its output. When the trial had ended, the rope would be disengaged.⁹

Such, in brief, was the procedure of the trials Smeaton completed in 1753. Yet in reporting on them in his 1759 paper, Smeaton would state clearly that a model always differs from a real machine in some respect: »Hence the common observation, that a thing may do very well in a model, that will not answer in large.«¹⁰ That said, the machine allowed Smeaton to measure the wheel's output by multiplying the weight lifted by the distance it was lifted. This product was compared with the quantity of water needed to activate the wheel. Smeaton called this the »natural effective power« of water.¹¹ The output of the waterwheel was defined by the physical terms work resp. power, neither of which was clearly defined at this time, of course.¹²

The raising of a weight, relative to the height to which it can be raised in a given time, is the most proper measure of power; or, in other words, if the weight raised is multiplied by the height to which it can be raised in a given time, the product is the measure of the power raising it.¹³

Work as a physical concept was introduced by Gaspar Coriolis in his 1826 »Calcul de l'effet des Machines,« where it is defined as the product of a force and the displacement caused by that force:

$$W = F s \tag{1}$$

Of course, in the context of *real* work, it is not the physical work as such that is of interest, but the power or rate at which the work is done:

⁷ For more biographical information cf. Alexander, 2008, pp. 19–21.

⁸ On models in general cf. Popplow, 2002, pp. 15–18.

⁹ Cf. Alexander, 2008, p. 21

¹⁰ Smeaton, 1759–1760, p. 101.

¹¹ *Ibid.*, p. 124.

¹² Cf. Steinle and Rammer, 2008, p. 17.

¹³ Smeaton, 1759–1760, p. 105.

$$P = \frac{\Delta W}{\Delta t} \quad (2)$$

In determining at which load and velocity of the wheel power is at a maximum, Smeaton was able to falsify Antoine Parent's antecedent conclusions and give the overshot wheel clear priority. What was the concrete historical situation?

Fountains, Channels, and Mills

Cultural practices of (physical) modeling can be found as early as antiquity. Pseudo-Aristotle followed the Archimedean analyses of simple machines in terms of an input-output relationship.¹⁴ Nevertheless, explicit experimentation with models began in the age of modern mechanics in the second half of the 17th century. The perhaps most prominent example of early physical modeling is the Machine de Marly, constructed by Arnold de Ville and Rennequin Sualem, the latter of whom was illiterate. De Ville ordered a model to be built of the machine that was constructed near St. Germain between June 1679 and the end of 1680. After trials demonstrated positive results, the king and his court approved the building of the final machine in Marly in 1681.¹⁵ We have no reliable sources for the size and the efficiency of the model, but the surviving accounts and the extended construction period suggest an extensive complex.¹⁶

When it came to mills, and especially watermills, there was a latent, inexplicit knowledge that every type of water mill provides maximum power at a particular speed.¹⁷ The analogue models served as a means to determine the optimal speed respective to the rules for their most efficient design. The Swedish scientist and inventor Christopher Polhem conducted a series of trials from 1701 to 1705 while he was director of the *Laboratorium mechanicum*. In 1705, he submitted an interim report to the Board of Mines. When he resumed work in 1710, he discovered »that two crucial quantities had been measured inaccurately throughout the whole series of measurements.«¹⁸ The reason for this was that the pendulum he used for time measurement had the wrong length.¹⁹ Polhem kept his failure secret. Although his work included strategies of parameter variation and optimization, he was never able to establish general rules for the design of waterwheels.

What was needed was a method in between. This need becomes only more clear if we also take a brief look at the mathematicians and their efforts to calculate the mechanics of waterwheels. In his 1704 research report »*Sur la plus grande perfection possible des machines*,« the French mathematician Antoine Parent discussed an ideal waterwheel without

14 Cf. Mitcham, 1994, p. 226.

15 Cf. Ergang, 1911.

16 A comparable and even more suggestive function was connected with the model of the Canal du Midi, which was realized from 1666–81 by the autodidact Pierre-Paul Riquet. Before starting actual construction, Riquet made a functional and nearly complete model of the channel near Toulouse. By then, the channel was regarded as an unfeasible project, but the model enabled Riquet to convince investors.

17 Cf. Lindqvist, 1990, p. 293 and Bleidick, 2019.

18 Lindqvist, 1990, p. 300.

19 Cf. *ibid.*, p. 197.

any friction. His analysis was based on two main assumptions. First, the force exerted on the wheel by the water was proportional to the square of the difference between the velocity of the water and the wheel. Second, Parent applied the principle of virtual velocities. This means that within a balance of forces, the sum of all work being done by the existing forces tends to zero for every infinitesimal virtual displacement of the systems. Moreover, Parent assumed that at any given time only one blade of the wheel was in contact with the water and that the water acted rectangularly and statically on the blade. Under this last assumption of a static force P exerted on the waterwheel, Parent's calculated value $4/27$ for the maximum amount of work VP is correct.²⁰ In reality, however, Parent's value is far too low and his analysis does not apply to all kinds of waterwheels under all conditions.²¹

Figure 2: A. Parent 1704: Waterwheel.

The most prominent initiative to make explicit the latent knowledge on waterwheels was launched in 1754 by the German Akademie der Wissenschaften in Göttingen. The most advantageous manner of employing the force of water was to be decided by scientific competition. The winner of the competition was Johann Albrecht Euler, the first of 13 children born to the famous Swiss mathematician Leonhard Euler. In his purely theory-driven approach, Euler applied Daniel Bernoulli's concept of living forces and his father's work on the

²⁰ Cf. Parent, 1704, p. 332, Capecchi, 2013, pp. 132–134 and Denny, 2004. In his examination of the undershot wheel, the French scientist Jean-Charles de Borda argued on the basis of an ideal wheel on a vertical axis. In doing so he applied both the law of conservation of energy and d'Alembert's principle. He found that the undershot waterwheel had an efficiency of $3/8$ or $1/2$, a value approximately double that established by Parent, cf. Borda, 1767, 285 and 285 and Capecchi, 2013, 134f. In a detailed but confusing comment, de Borda explains why the values are so far apart. The reason he provides is that because in reality not only one blade enters the water, the effect is therefore not proportional to the square of the difference in speed, but rather directly proportional to it. Since the text provides no arguments for this supposition, this passage remains very murky.

²¹ Cf. T. S. Reynolds, 1979, p. 276 and Steinle and Rammer, 2008, p. 20.

Segner wheel – a horizontal wheel developed by Andreas Segner in 1749 – to hydrodynamics.

*Praedipuum est conservatio virium vivarum, seu, ut ego loquor, aequalitas inter descensum actualem ascensumque potentialem.*²²

In his submission to the Akademie der Wissenschaften, Euler proves first that – as long as the buckets are big enough – the effective power of a gravity or overshot waterwheel is identical whether the wheel is at rest or in uniform motion. Given this, the overshot wheel's result is the product of the water's weight and the fall. In the event that all the water is accommodated by the buckets, the efficiency of the gravity wheel would be 100 percent and hence much higher than the theoretical maximum $8/27$ of impulse wheels.²³ Hence, Euler came to the conclusion that overshot wheels were much more effective than undershot wheels. But what was the physical difference between impulse and gravity wheels?

Figure 3: I. Newton 1661–1665: Gravity Wheel.

Even before the 18th century, weight and impulse were recognized as distinctly different forces. But there was great confusion about the advantages and disadvantages of these two forces and how to apply them most efficiently.²⁴ Prior to 1750, practical work and theoretical analysis went hand in hand, and the diversity of concrete topological situations did not permit waterwheels to be theorized independently of local conditions. In regions with low falls and high water volumes, undershot waterwheels were naturally preferred. Hence, impulse and gravity seemed to be equally powerful – depending only on the motive power of the stream. Or, as the British natural philosopher John Th. Desaguliers summarizes:

It is a difficult thing, and requires some Experiments to determine, whether there should be any Impulse given in an Over-shot Mill; or rather a Wheel made of such a large Diameter as to receive the Water without any Percussion, by which means it may go with less Water [...] For my part, I can determine nothing certain in this for want of sufficient Experiments.²⁵

²² Bernoulli, 1738, p. 11.

²³ Cf. Euler, 1754, 14 and 32.

²⁴ Cf. T. S. Reynolds, 1979, p. 271.

²⁵ Desaguliers, 1744, p. 532.

But there is still another, more epistemic reason for mixing gravity and impulse. Since Galileo and Newton, the system of physical knowledge had argued from the dichotomy of matter and force. All natural phenomena are caused by particles of matter in motion, and the interaction of these particles is by contact or impulse. This leads to the strange conclusion that even gravity must be explained as an impact effect of extremely tiny particles. In Newton's Trinity College Notebook, one can find a depiction of gravitational force acting on a vertical wheel suspended on a horizontal axis. The left half of the wheel is shielded against the gravitational rain such that the »rays of gravity« set the wheel in permanent rotation.²⁶

The gravity of bodys is as their solidity, because all bodys descend equall spaces in equall times consideration being had to the Resistance of the aire &c.²⁷

In summary, it can be said that despite all theoretical uncertainties, experimental discrepancies, and methodological contradictions, all the approaches have one point in common. They all agree that the efficiency of the waterwheel must be regarded – and calculated – in relation to the difference between the velocity of the water and the wheel. And as a direct consequence, mutual disturbances of both movements should be minimized in order to achieve maximum effect. This raises the question – just because flow patterns are directly observable – of whether this optical feedback mechanism has any practical or theoretical impact for experimentation with waterwheels. If so, this would strongly support my introductory thesis that this practice of measuring can be regarded as a form of analogue simulation.

»Spent in Changing their Figure«

Such was the situation in which Smeaton performed his experiments in 1752 and 1753, when he began taking measurements of the undershot wheel in order to falsify Parent's assumption that an undershot wheel could produce a maximum effect equal to $4/27$ of the water column's weight.²⁸ He was able to show that the theoretical efficiency of the undershot wheel was 0.32, but could reach 50 percent for large wheels, which was three times Parent's prediction.²⁹ In his second paper, he even went on to say that »as the whole would be the limit for the overshot mills, if it were possible to set aside all friction, resistance from the

²⁶ Newton, 1661–1665, p. 121v.

²⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 121v.

²⁸ At around the same time, the French mathematician Antoine de Parcieux was also able to falsify Parent's impulse theory. De Parcieux was invited by Mme. de Pompadour to find a solution for regular problems with the chateau's water supply. He made a series of nine experiments, each repeated up to twelve times, to find out the best combination of descending and ascending weights. He concluded that the slower the waterwheel moved, the better the machine worked. The gravity wheel was 20 in in diameter with 48 buckets and an axle with a drum of different diameters allowed him to verify the rotational velocity of the wheel. Cf. Parcieux, 1754, p. 674. Hence, the velocity of the wheel could be changed either by using different load weights or by using axles of different diameters. This is the first time that a model succeeded in simulating parallel data with more than two parameters or in more than two dimensions. Nevertheless, De Parcieux's experiments were not simulations in the strict sense of the term, because the model grew directly out of a practical problem and was designed to confirm conclusions he had already reached. Cf. T. S. Reynolds, 1979, p. 281.

²⁹ Cf. Smeaton, 1759–1760, p. 113 and Smeaton, 1776, p. 456.

air, &c.«³⁰ It can thus be said that the average efficiency of overshot wheels was double that of undershot wheels.³¹ And at the same time, this overall result shows a deep interest not only in the practical conditions of waterwheels, but also in the nature of their movement: Smeaton tried to explain the difference between impulse and gravity wheels in terms of the internal behavior of the water, which – and this is key – can be observed directly as a figure of these movements:

*nonelastic bodies, when acting by their impulse or collision, communicate only a part of their original power; the other part being spent in changing their figure in consequence of the stroke.*³²

From this we can conclude that Smeaton tried to explain the difference between weight and impulse from the observation of flow patterns. These observations led him to what is historically the first clear distinction between the weight and impulse force of water:

It will appear, in the course of the following deductions, that the effect of the gravity of descending bodies is very different from the effect of the stroke of such as are *non-elastic*, tho' generated by an equal mechanical power.³³

There is thus a clear rupture between the experiments of Smeaton and de Parcieux, with their focus on quantitative variables, and those of their predecessors such as Riquet or Sualem.³⁴ In the following systematic reconstruction of Smeaton's main 1759 paper, I will thus pay special attention to hidden references to optical impressions and their epistemic relevance.

For his calculations, Smeaton introduced the concept of »virtual or effective head.«³⁵ This parameter is based on the velocity of the waterwheel being the same whether the water strikes it or not. The value of this parameter was determined by the use of a counterweight at the maximum load that does not lead to a speed reduction of the waterwheel. Of course, this calculation is based on the assumption that maximum effect is achieved when the waterwheel rotates at the velocity of the water. In this case, no disturbances or water turbulence occur, which is a visible hint that the wheel is operating at maximal efficiency.

Now, on the basis of this concept of virtual head, Smeaton recorded thirteen different data sets. In doing so, he introduced a method of systematically varying parameters through experimentation. This method doesn't require a full theoretical understanding of the mechanism, because the mechanism itself – or the model of the mechanism – produced data by simulation.³⁶ But on the other hand, the introduction of the concept of a virtual head

30 Smeaton, 1776, pp. 456–457.

31 Cf. Smeaton, 1759–1760, p. 130 and Capecchi, 2013, p. 136.

32 Smeaton, 1759–1760, p. 103.

33 *Ibid.*, p. 125.

34 Differently than Euler, however, Smeaton and de Parcieux did not apply scientific principles, but instead used more or less traditional technological tools that came out of mechanics and which they applied to hydrodynamics. Johann Euler, on the other hand, directly applied science to a technological problem in order to prove the superior efficiency of the overshot wheel.

35 Cf. Alexander, 2008, pp. 22–24 and Smeaton, 1759–1760, pp. 110–113.

36 Cf. Rosen, 2012, pp. 126–129.

shows that Smeaton's »interest was broader than immediate practical utility.«³⁷ His simulation aimed to understand the mechanisms of matter in motion. I will come back to this essential point later.

Smeaton starts by introducing the term power as the product of the weight and the height to which the weight is raised in a given time. This is in line with the current definition of potential energy or mechanical stroke work

$$W = Fs = mgh. \quad (3)$$

The height can be linked to the velocity of the water by recourse to some older physics: according to the Italian scientist Evangelista Torricelli and the French mathematician Pierre Varignon, the speed of efflux, v , of a fluid is proportional to the square root of the height h of the fluid: $v = \sqrt{2gh}$.³⁸ From this, the »height of head« follows directly from the speed of efflux as $h = \frac{v^2}{2g}$. Multiplying this value for the »height of head« by the corresponding water weight, according to the definition of the power in equation 3, gives the »original power of water.« What this means is that the amount of power provided by a given quantity of water is only determined by its current velocity

$$W = mgh = mg \frac{v^2}{2g} = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 = T. \quad (4)$$

This short calculation shows that v^2 is proportional to h , or that mv^2 can be adjusted to the product of weight and height. Behind this lies a complex debate – which we will leave out here – on measuring the force of bodies in action by the product of their mass and velocity, or by the product of their weight and the square of its velocity.³⁹

From this it follows that the first step in Smeaton's trials was to determine the »real velocity of the water, at the instant of its striking the wheel.«⁴⁰ The procedure is as follows: initially, the wheel is set in rotation by the water without any counterweight.⁴¹ For this, Smeaton determined a value of 80 rotations per minute.⁴² Because of the internal friction of the waterwheel, however, this value does not correspond to the real velocity of the water flow. Internal friction tends to slow down the rotational speed of the waterwheel, meaning that the velocity of the water before it encounters the paddles must be higher.

As we will see, this is precisely the point where the practice of simulation comes into play. Smeaton accelerates the rotation of the waterwheel by applying a counterweight in the same direction as the water flow. In other words, this counterweight compensates for the retardation caused by internal friction. By comparing the velocities with and without water flow, Smeaton arrives at a value of 1 lb. 8 oz. (3,658 kg) for a counterweight at which the water flow neither retards nor accelerates the constant idling speed of 86 revolutions

³⁷ Alexander, 2008, p. 23.

³⁸ Cf. Varignon, 1725, p. 52 and Dugas, 1988, pp. 147, 226–227.

³⁹ Cf. Hankins, 1965.

⁴⁰ Smeaton, 1759–1760, p. 107.

⁴¹ Cf. *ibid.*, p. 107.

⁴² Cf. *ibid.*, p. 110. For all his measurements, Smeaton uses one minute as the basic unit of time.

per minute.⁴³ Now, this value corresponds exactly to the rotational speed of the waterwheel without any internal friction, because all friction effects are compensated by the action of the counterweight. The velocity of the water can thus be calculated as the product of the number of revolutions and the circumference of the wheel:⁴⁴

$$v = r\omega \tag{5}$$

$$= 75 \cdot 86 \text{ in/min} = 190.5 \cdot 86 \text{ cm/min} = 16,383 \text{ cm/min} = 273 \text{ cm/s} \tag{6}$$

$$= 8,96 \text{ ft/s} \tag{7}$$

This setting raises the following two questions: first, how is it even possible that this measurement strategy could provide accurate results? And second, how did Smeaton determine an identical rotational speed for the waterwheel? To start with the second question, one could set up long measurement series and try to find the most similar values. Smeaton, however, took a different path: »The water [...] becomes a *regulator* of the wheel's motion.«⁴⁵ He observed whether engaging the counterweight during operation by means of a gear coupling changed the rotational speed. His experimental setting thus did not consist of a discrete series of measurements, but of a simulation whose constantly changing parameters were under continual observation. But what exactly are these parameters, or how can one observe the rotational speed of a waterwheel as differences between the velocity of the wheel and the water? Smeaton's answer is as short as it is precise: by means of the water itself. The water flow serves as the medium enabling the observation of differences of speed. Laminar flow means: no friction and hence identical velocities. By contrast, turbulent flow means: friction and loss of power due to different velocities.

Of course, to read Smeaton's 1759 paper in this way would be consistent with his biography. Nearly all of his engineering tasks were in some way connected to water: the Ed-dystone Lighthouse, the River Calder Navigation, masonry bridges, canals, harbors, basins, drainages, and piers – not to mention more than 50 watermills.⁴⁶ Hence one could say that Smeaton's own life was driven by water.

In 1794, a printed »Catalogue of Books, including the Library of John Smeaton« was issued by the London bookseller John Edgerton. Although it is impossible to reliably identify all the books belonging to Smeaton's library, we can assume that the titles listed by A. W. Skempton represent the state of physical knowledge at the time.⁴⁷ Of special interest for the simulation of water flows is the book »The motion of fluids, natural and artificial; in particular that of the air and water« by Martin Clare, a copy of which is signed by Smeaton.⁴⁸ In this book, Clare writes

that by the *Vis Inertiae* of Matter, the Water endeavouring still to continue in a State of Rest, the Vessel cannot in an Instant communicate its Motion to it; it not

43 Cf. Smeaton, 1759–1760, p. 110.

44 Cf. *ibid.*, p. 107.

45 Cf. *ibid.*, p. 108.

46 Cf. Skempton, 1981, pp. 1–2.

47 Cf. *ibid.*, pp. 247–250.

48 Cf. Clare, 1747.

being a consistent of a fixed Body like itself, but a Fluid: The Liquor therefore perseveres for a small Time in its first State of Rest, while the Vessel makes forward, and therefore seems to move a contrary Way. But when the Liquor has the Motion of the Vessel fully communicated to it, and begins to move with a Velocity equal to that of the Vessel, they than proceed very quietly together.⁴⁹

A certain amount of time is thus required before the waterwheel and the water will reach the same speed. This state of optimal power transmission is easily recognized: it's all quiet. No turbulence, no vortexes, no swell.

The more perfect a Fluid is, the more easily will it yield to all Impressions; and the more easily will the Parts unite and coalesce, when separated. A perfect Fluid is that, whose Parts are put into Motion by the *least* Force imaginable: An imperfect one is that, whose Parts yield to a *small* Force, not the *least*. 'Tis probable, that in Nature there is no perfect Fluid.⁵⁰

Figure 4: B. de Bélidor 1737–1735: Water Flow in a Mill.

Water can serve as a medium because it is an imperfect fluid. This raises the question of whether there is any concrete evidence of the flow pattern's visibility and its technical exploitation. Smeaton's library also contained the comprehensive four-volume compendium »Architecture hydraulique« by the French engineer Bernard Forest de Bélidor, which was issued from 1737 to 1753. Although Bélidor does not explicitly address flow patterns, we can actually *see* this knowledge in the figures. A closer look at fig. 4 allows us to recognize that the concentration of the lines indicating the water flow in the mill varies.⁵¹ While the water

49 Clare, 1747, p. 105.

50 *Ibid.*, pp. 8–9.

51 Cf. Bélidor, 1737, p. 284.

runs down the influx channel, its speed continuously increases. In the figure, this is depicted by the dotted and slightly rippled lines whose density increases as the water comes closer to the wheel. Additionally, the hatching directly behind the wheel illustrates disturbances or disordered power.

The explanation for Bélidor's depiction must be sought in another publication, however. Smeaton's library was presumably also home to the two-volume book »An introduction to a general system of hydrostaticks and hydraulicks, philosophical and practical« published by the British garden designer Stephen Switzer. In volume one, he writes with reference to fig. 5:

Now, because Water is suppos'd by some to be of a viscous Nature, and its Parts a little join'd together, the Water D E will carry along with it that which is immediately above, with almost the same Velocity which it has self, and afterwards that which is at F G, which moving likewise of it self, by Reason of its Inclination, goes a little faster than the Water D E.⁵²

Of course, this is an idealized modeling of the water flow, as the »less the Irregularities are, the more true Motions agree with what has been said.«⁵³ Switzer's ideal fluids behave like solid bodies. In water flows whose speeds differ internally, »the united Force of the Water is broken; its Strength in a great Measure lost.«⁵⁴ These speed differences, which appear as turbulence and other disturbances, thus have to be avoided. Or, in a nutshell: Bélidor's illustrations plus Switzer's epistemology defines Smeaton's agenda.

Figure 5: St. Switzer 1727–1729: Water Flow in a River.

Let's return to John Smeaton and his 1759 publication. Smeaton was able to determine by immediately observing the flow pattern whether the water and the wheel had the same speed. Although there is no explicit reference in the text, the fundamental parameter of the experiment is obtained by visual assessment of the flow pattern of a dynamical system.⁵⁵ This all points to the same conclusion: the knowledge of flow patterns is a tacit, practical,

52 Switzer, 1727, p. 264.

53 *Ibid.*, p. 266.

54 *Ibid.*, p. 260.

55 Cf. Alexander, 2008, p. 21.

or implicit knowledge.⁵⁶ It is something that a person like John Smeaton *does* every single day working on the construction of harbors, channels, or watermills. And while on the one hand of course it is a deeply embodied and experienced practice, on the other hand it is such a complex and multifaceted knowledge that it can't become part of the paper as a symbolic system. The only hints we can find are some rippled lines in the depictions from Bélidor's compendium.

The answer to the first question I can touch on only briefly in the context of this paper. In 1868, the Scottish scientist James Clerk Maxwell introduced the first theoretical analysis of James Watt's regulator. Because it provided a mathematical theory of the governor, this paper is regarded as one of the founding documents of cybernetics.⁵⁷ In this context, I believe that Smeaton's experimental setting is based on the idea of communication and control, and that it is therefore a proto-cybernetic system.

Returning to Smeaton's paper, we can derive the height of a water column corresponding to a theoretical machine without any friction or »virtual head« directly from the velocity of the water:

$$h = \frac{v^2}{2g} = \frac{2.73^2}{2 \cdot 9.81} \text{m} = 0,38 \text{ m} = 15 \text{ in} \quad (8)$$

According to Smeaton's definition of power, this is the product of the virtual height and the weight of the volume of water that flows through the mill in a given period, which in Smeaton's trials is always one minute. The question thus arises as to how we can determine the volume of water. Smeaton solved this problem by counting pump strokes (per minute), and found that 12 pump strokes raised the water level or »head« by 21 in or 53,3 cm. By using a float to monitor the water level and the pump to keep it constant, Smeaton was able to correlate the number of pump strokes to the amount of water that flowed through the mill model in the same period. This shows once again that Smeaton's approach did not involve mutually independent series of measurements; on the contrary, his experimental setting was a dynamical system in which several parameters were being communicated and controlled while the experiment was running. The various measurements were only possible because the simulation system was in *continuous* operation:

During a trial the pump was operated with a steady rhythm and consistent length of stroke, to keep the level in the cistern and the head of water even and to keep track of the amount of water expended.⁵⁸

This continuous operation and water flow in turn enabled the observation of the flow pattern with or without counterweight.

Given a cross-section of 105,8 in², the flow rate per 12 pump strokes is

⁵⁶ This situation changes in the second half of the 19th century, cf. i. e. Redtenbacher, 1846, p. II or Weisbach, 1865, 398 ff. .

⁵⁷ Cf. Maxwell, 2002.

⁵⁸ Alexander, 2008, p. 21.

$$12 \text{ strokes} \hat{=} 105,8 \text{ in}^2 \cdot 21 \text{ in} = 2221,8 \text{ in}^3 = 36\,408,78 \text{ cm}^3 \quad (9)$$

$$\hat{=} 36,41 \text{ kg} = 80 \text{ lb } 4,3 \text{ oz} \quad (10)$$

A simple proportion argument of pump strokes per kilogram to pump strokes per minute yields the final value for the amount of water per minute:⁵⁹

$$\text{water/min} = \frac{39,5 \text{ strokes/min} \cdot 36,41 \text{ kilogram}}{12 \text{ strokes}} = 119,85 \text{ kg/min} = 264 \text{ lb } 3,6 \text{ oz} \quad (11)$$

According to his aforementioned definition on p. 105, Smeaton obtains for the theoretical maximum of the waterwheel's power being the product of water amount and »virtual head« the following value:⁶⁰

$$P_{virt} = \frac{\Delta W}{\Delta t} = F \cdot s = F_G \cdot h = m \cdot g \cdot h \quad (12)$$

$$= \frac{119,85 \text{ kg} \cdot 0,38 \text{ m} \cdot 9,81 \text{ m/s}^2}{60 \text{ s}} \quad (13)$$

$$= 7,45 \text{ W} = 0,01 \text{ PS} \quad (14)$$

We now come to the second major step in Smeaton's experimental setting, which is to determine the efficiency of the waterwheel.⁶¹ This requires sorting out two things: first, the amount of water power lost by friction or air resistance; and second, the real velocity of the water when it hits the paddles. Taking the same amount of water as in the equation 11, or, as Smeaton puts it, »the real expence of water,« this motive power will raise a working weight to a height that is, due to friction effects, lower than the theoretical value or »virtual head.«⁶² In Smeaton's words, »the value of the friction, resistance, &c. in any given case« defines the »effect of that power.«⁶³ By varying the working weights – and the respective rotational speed of the waterwheel – the maximum effect of the machine can be determined. Hence, the second major step of Smeaton's experiment starts by varying the parameter of the counterweight or working weight in order to systematically find the optimal rotational speed, »the greatest product, or *maximum* effect.«⁶⁴ In the table on p. 110, the optimal value is listed in the fifth row: at a counterweight of 8 lb (3,63 kg) the waterwheel makes 30 turns per minute.

If the diameter of the wheel's axis – 9 in and a factor of 1/2 because of the pulley system – is added to this, then the value for the raising of the weight is 135 in/min (3,43 m/min). In order to derive for this power the maximum achievable effect for an ideal and frictionless

59 Cf. Smeaton, 1759–1760, p. 111 with the final value of 264.7 lb.

60 In the Anglo-American measuring system the value for the power is 3970, cf. *ibid.*, p. 111.

61 Cf. *ibid.*, p. 106.

62 Cf. *ibid.*, p. 107.

63 Cf. *ibid.*, p. 107.

64 Cf. *ibid.*, p. 109.

N°	Weight. lb. oz.	Turns in a min.	Product.
1	4 0	45	180
2	5 0	42	210
3	6 0	36 $\frac{1}{4}$	217 $\frac{1}{4}$
4	7 0	33 $\frac{3}{4}$	236 $\frac{1}{4}$
5	8 0	30	240 maximum.
6	9 0	26 $\frac{1}{2}$	238 $\frac{1}{2}$
7	10 0	22	220
8	11 0	16 $\frac{1}{2}$	181 $\frac{1}{2}$
9	12	* ceased working.	

Figure 6: J. Smeaton 1759: Maximum Power of Water Wheel.

machine, Smeaton has to take all possible friction losses of the machine into account. The experimental strategy for this is identical to the setting's first step: Smeaton uses a counterweight to bring the waterwheel to the same speed *without* water flow: »It is evident that this weight will be nearly equal to all friction and resistance taken together.«⁶⁵ Hence, given an identical flow pattern, the counterweight is exactly equal to the friction of the experimental system. Additionally, the weight of the pulley itself has to be taken doubly into account, which adds up to a total friction of 9,375 lb or 4,25 kg.⁶⁶ The effective power is calculated as:

$$P_{eff} = \frac{4,25 \text{ kg} \cdot 9,81 \text{ m/s}^2 \cdot 3,43 \text{ m}}{60 \text{ s}} = 2,38 \text{ W} \quad (15)$$

Now, the efficiency of the waterwheel is defined by the ratio of the virtual and the effective power:

$$\frac{P_{eff}}{P_{virt}} = \frac{2.38}{7.45} = 0.32 \quad (16)$$

However, this value for the efficiency has to be adjusted for the fact that not all of the water's power is transformed into the rotational energy of the wheel – simply because the water also flows behind the paddles. This means that if the waterwheel rotates at 30 revolutions per minute, then the water is so to speak released at exactly this flow speed. Hence, the flow velocity is

$$v = r\omega \quad (17)$$

$$= 75 \cdot 30 \text{ in/min} = 190.5 \cdot 30 \text{ cm/min} = 95,25 \text{ cm/s} \quad (18)$$

$$= 3,125 \text{ ft/s} \quad (19)$$

This equals a height of the water column of

⁶⁵ Cf. Smeaton, 1759–1760, p. 109.

⁶⁶ Cf. *ibid.*, p. 112.

$$h = \frac{v^2}{2g} = \frac{0.9525^2}{2 \cdot 9.81} \text{ m} = 0,046 \text{ m} = 1,82 \text{ in} \quad (20)$$

and a corresponding power of

$$P_{water} = m \cdot g \cdot h \quad (21)$$

$$= \frac{119,85 \text{ kg} \cdot 0,046 \text{ m} \cdot 9,81 \text{ m/s}^2}{60 \text{ s}} \quad (22)$$

$$= 0,90 \text{ W}. \quad (23)$$

The theoretically available power of the water is reduced by that amount:

$$P_{tot} = P_{virt} - P_{water} = 6,55 \text{ W}. \quad (24)$$

And hence the final result for the theoretical efficiency of the waterwheel is:⁶⁷

$$\frac{P_{eff}}{P_{tot}} = \frac{2.38}{6.55} = 0,36. \quad (25)$$

So we can note that Smeaton obtains a significantly higher value for the theoretical efficiency of an undershot wheel than the value of $4/27$ established by Parent.

Calculus Imaginarium

Smeaton's simulation system relates two quantities in a dynamical way: the virtual energy of the water as practically available power and the real energy of the waterwheel as actually achieved power. This gives rise to the central question of why Smeaton used as his basic reference for calculating the machine's efficiency the experimentally very complicated parameter of the water's »virtual height,« which is based on an optical assessment of the water flow, rather than its »total fall.«⁶⁸ The answer to this question brings us back to the beginning of this paper and the Franklin Institute's 1,381 experiments. The first experiment reported used a pitch-back overshot wheel with elbow buckets and a close breast.⁶⁹ In the first three columns, three different heads are listed: the height of water above the aperture, the height above the top and above the bottom of the bucket.⁷⁰ It therefore follows that every measurement starts with these parameters as fixed values.

This all sounds quite easy and convenient – at least at first glance. Digging into the details of the report reveals some unforeseen problems, however:

The head, above the top of the bucket, was estimated for the overshot aperture, [...] by the height of the water above the highest point of the wheel; and that above

⁶⁷ Cf. Smeaton, 1759–1760, p. 113.

⁶⁸ Alexander, 2008, p. 23.

⁶⁹ Cf. Anonymous, 1831, p. 85.

⁷⁰ Cf. *ibid.*, p. 82.

the bottom of the bucket, by the height above the highest point of the soleing of the wheel. The heads, above the tops of the buckets, upon which the water first struck, were estimated for apertures, [...] by the height of the water, above a point in each aperture, one-half an inch distant from the periphery of the wheel.⁷¹

The report uses the term estimation where the reader would expect measurement. Obviously, it is impossible to give an exact value for the different heights because the water flow that strikes the wheel has no precise height. For the scientists of the Franklin Institute this is not a problem. But for John Smeaton, the engineer who observed and worked with water flows on a daily basis, determining this height is part of the experimental setting itself. There is no fixed head beyond the problem of how to understand the movement of fluids like water. The head itself is a dynamical process and it can only be determined by observing the flow pattern.

TABLE A.—PART I.
CHUTE No. 1.—Gate a. Pitch-back over-shot. Elbow buckets. Close breast. Water let on at upper centre of wheel.

No. of Experiment.	Head of water above.			Width of Aperture.	Weight raised.	Friction.	Sum of friction and weight raised.	Height raised.	Time.	Velocity per second.	Wt of water expended.	Head and fall.	Power.	Effect.	Ratio, power being 1.	Maximum defect.	Velocity at maximum.	Observations.		
	Bun. of gate.	Top of bkt.	Bun. of bkt.																	
	Feet.	Feet.	Feet.	In.	Pds.	Pounds.	Pounds.	Feet.	Secs.	Feet.	Pds.	Feet.								
1	2.75	3.00	3.60	0.50	237	44.54	301.54	41.5	33	11.84	835	23.0	192050	125139	.652	-	-	-	Water carried above lower centre of wheel before it was discharged from buckets.	
2					416	47.32	463.32		40	9.77	1100		253000	192278	.759					
3					463	48.14	511.14		44	8.88	1200		276000	212123	.768					
4					772	53.54	825.54		69	5.66	1825		419750	342599	.816					
5					875	55.34	930.34		74	5.28	2025		465750	386091	.829	.829	5.28	Water discharged at bottom of wheel.		
6					931	56.32	987.32		83	4.71	2200		506000	409738	.809					
7					978	57.14	1035.14		86	4.54	2300		529000	429583	.812					
8					1081	58.94	1139.94		94	4.16	2575		592250	473075	.799					
9	2.75	3.00	3.60	1.00	1493	73.85	1566.85	41.5	68	5.75	3450	23.0	793500	630243	.820					
10					1549	76.22	1625.22		70	5.58	3525		810750	674466	.832					
11					1596	78.22	1674.22		72	5.43	3600		828000	694801	.839	.839	5.43			
12					1699	82.59	1781.59		80	4.88	3925		902750	739360	.818					
13	2.75	3.00	3.60	1.25	1905	91.33	1996.33	41.5	66	5.92	4350	23.0	1000500	828477	.828					
14					2008	95.70	2103.70		70	5.58	4550		1046500	873035	.834	.834	5.58			
15					2111	100.07	2211.07		74	5.28	4810		1106300	917594	.829					
16	2.25	2.50	3.10	0.75	875	55.34	930.34	41.5	57	6.86	2115	22.50	475787	386091	.811					
17					1081	58.94	1139.94		69	5.66	2575		579375	473075	.815					
18					1184	60.74	1244.74		75	5.21	2800		630000	516567	.820	.820	5.21			
19					1287	65.11	1352.11		82	4.77	3050		686250	561126	.817					
20					1390	69.48	1459.48		93	4.20	3380		749250	605684	.808					

Figure 7: Franklin Institute 1831: Over-shot wheel.

Or, to be even more precise: as a practical engineer, Smeaton is primarily interested in the dynamical relationship between the virtual and the real power. This is what he investigates by means of his simulation system. His dynamical experimental setup allows him to directly observe disturbances in the water flow and to determine these two quantities by engaging counterweights during operation to reduce disturbances. This dynamical compensation by means of counterweights marks the difference between virtual and real power. The significance of his experiment is generated by differences gained from the observation of flow

⁷¹ Anonymous, 1831, pp. 82–83.

patterns:

He could easily tell how much work a waterwheel had done; what he could not determine was how well it had used the motion, or force or power, that made work possible.⁷²

To put it pointedly: Smeaton eliminated the friction of his experimental machine in order to make the flow configurations visible so he could determine the practical available power or »virtual head.«

Appendix

Flow patterns are complex phenomena. Above a certain speed, any flow gets complex. The patterns become irregular, inhomogeneous and chaotic. Turbulence is highly sensitive to any disturbance: even the slightest change of circumstances can lead to massive effects. This is why weather forecasts can never be reliable. Smeaton observes turbulence, sharing in an age-old fascination for such phenomena. Leonardo da Vinci depicted turbulent flows in order to understand their internal order.⁷³

Figure 8: Leonardo da Vinci 1510–13: Studies of flowing water, with notes.

However, a systematic and mathematically reliable approach to these phenomena wasn't possible before the end of the 19th century. On 15 March 1883, the British physicist Osborne Reynolds used partially inked water to observe the transition to turbulence in pipe flow.⁷⁴

⁷² Alexander, 2008, p. 18.

⁷³ Cf. the digital simulation of Leonardo's setting in Monaghan and Kajtar, 2014.

⁷⁴ Cf. O. Reynolds, 1883.

More than 125 years after Reynolds' paper, we are still unable to fully explain the nature of this transition.⁷⁵

Figure 9: O. Reynolds 1883: Pipe flow.

Although digital simulations are now helping solve the differential equations for typical flow patterns in a numerical way, analogue model building is still an important strategy to explore complex hydrodynamic processes. It might seem that the 5,000 hour-long wind tunnel trials that shaped the wings of the Concorde should have been consigned to history by the development of modern supercomputers.⁷⁶ But as we learned from the recently finished Elbphilharmonie in Hamburg, the acoustic design of concert halls still needs analogue modeling – in this case a wooden 1:10 scale model of the large auditorium, filled with hundreds of little rag dolls. The context of current digital and analogue simulation practices recalls the special care John Smeaton took in formulating his own experimental setting:

It is evident, that the *virtual head* bears no certain proportion to the *head of water*.⁷⁷

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⁷⁵ Cf. Eckhardt, 2009.

⁷⁶ Cf. Kassung, 2019.

⁷⁷ Smeaton, 1759–1760, p. 122.

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